

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl orthovanadate was prepared by the ammonia method¹³ as given below :

Vanadium oxytrichloride (VOCl_3) was first prepared by the reaction of Thionyl chloride with vanadium pentoxide. It was treated with dry ethanol and dry ammonia gas passed in the reaction mixture. The resulting ethyl orthovanadate was filtered off leaving behind solid ammonium chloride. It was then fractionated to remove excess of ethanol, benzene and ammonia, followed by distillation under reduced pressure ($102^\circ/9.0$ mm). It was analysed and the analysis is given in the table.

The Schiff bases used in these reactions were prepared by the condensation of aldehyde with amine in the requisite amount.

Glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable quickfit joints was used to exclude moisture. All fractionations were carried out on a column (about 30 cm. long) packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total condensation variable take-off still head.

Reaction between oxo-vanadium ethoxide and bis-salicylidene-ethylenediamine in equimolar ratio : An exothermic reaction occurred, when Schiff base was mixed to a benzene solution of ethyl orthovanadate. The mixture was refluxed under a fractionating column for 3 hrs. The binary azeotrope of benzene-ethanol was slowly fractionated off and the remaining benzene was removed at a high reflux ratio. It was then dried under reduced pressure, and the resulting compound was found to be insoluble in benzene.

Similarly the reaction between oxo-vanadium ethoxide and salicylidene-2-hydroxy-*n*-propylamine was also carried out and for brevity all the results are summarized in the following table.

TABLE

Analyses of $\overset{0}{V}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ and its Schiff Base Derivatives

S.No.	Reactants (g)	Molecular formula State & Yield (g)	% of Ethanol in the azeotrope		Analysis%	
			Found	Calc.	Metal	Nitrogen
1.	$\text{VOCl}_3(25)$ + $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}(35)$ + NH_3	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$, Reddish Yellow liquid (20.2)	Found 25.01 Calc. 25.21		66.15 66.86	— —
2.	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ (2.04) + Bis-salicylidene- ethylenediamine (2.68)	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N})$, Green solid (3.56)	Found 0.921 Calc. 0.929		13.33 13.47	7.38 7.40
3.	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ (2.03) + Salicylidene-2-hydroxy- <i>n</i> -propyl amine (1.79)	$\text{VO}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{N})$, Brown solid (2.55)	Found 0.920 Calc. 0.925		17.95 17.60	4.79 4.84

Infrared Measurements : IR spectra of the Schiff bases and their oxo-vanadium (V) complexes have been recorded (4000–400 cm^{-1}) with Perkin-Elmer 337 Grating Infrared spectrophotometer using KBr optics. The frequencies are given below :

Bissalicylidene-ethylenediamine ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$)

3380wb, 1630s, 1650(m), 1575vs, 1520w, 1490vs, 1455vs, 1420m, 1286vs, 1250m, 1222m, 1202s, 1152vs, 1118m, 1047(vs), 1026vs, 985s, 975s, 940m, 902m, 862vs, 776s, 758m, 752m, 743s, 648s, 561m, 485m, 470m, 428.

(VO)(OEt) ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$) :

3350bw., 1620vs, 1601vs, 1520m, 1435vs, 1360s, 1320m, 1298m, 1268s, 1248s, 1231w, 1200(m), 1150vs, 1125s, 1083m, 1023m, 968vs, 952vs, 900s, 808m, 790s, 753vs, 643m, 618vs, 583(s), 563m, 543w, 511w, 440vs.

Salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2$) :

3380sb, 3054vw, 1625vs, 1570s, 1505m, 1445m, 1430m, 1405m, 1355m, 1340m, 1280s, 1221m, 1150m, 1135m, 1083w, 1043m, 1023m, 983w, 941m, 883m, 753vs, 733m, 648w, 568vw, 443w.

VO(OEt) ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2$) :

1625s, 1590m, 1540m, 1450vs, 1370m, 1315m, 1300s, 1285s, 1222m, 1148m, 1122m, 1082w, 1040s, 1028m, 980vs, 960vs, 935m, 905m, 868w, 847w, 808m, 748s, 730w, 715w, 663(b.s), 672m, 578m, 558w, 543m, 515m, 435s.

On comparing the spectra of the Schiff bases and their corresponding Oxo-Vanadium (V) complexes it may be inferred that the broad and medium bands in 3600–3100 cm^{-1} region may be due to hydrogen bonded -OH group in the Schiff base which totally disappear in the corresponding metal-Schiff base complexes, showing chelation. The C = C/C = N stretching frequency bands occur at 1605 and 1630 cm^{-1} in the salicylidene-2-hydroxy-n-propylamine and bis-salicylidene-ethylenediamine respectively. These frequencies, however appear in almost the same region in the corresponding metal complexes. Due to the complicated nature of the spectra the stretching V = O vibrations cannot be assigned with certainty. Most probably strong bands in 960–980 cm^{-1} range may be tentatively assigned to these vibrations. Further, the bands appearing in the range of 578–663 cm^{-1} in both the complexes may be attributed to metal-oxygen and metal-nitrogen bands.

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